

Deep Learning Approaches for Orchard Mapping

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Abstract— Deep learning for semantic segmentation on orchard mapping aims at tracing the location of the tree canopy while considering the seasonal factor, the degree of the trees, and the amount of weed cover. There are many other factors that contribute to the inaccuracies in the segmentation which include the season, canopy size, weed cover, the state of the background soil, and raw soil. The research suggested employs an array of training and testing datasets that represent different conditions of the orchard. A variant of deep learning based convolutional nets is employed in this investigation with the application of U-net network algorithms. In this way, the area covered by the tree canopy can be mapped automatically from UAV images... The process of automatic segmentation of oblique images of tree canopies taken from a UAV will benefit the farmers in designing all in one tools. These factors then allow for the tree's given volume to be figured out.

Keywords— UAV images, deep learning, semantic segmentation, tree canopy, U-net

I. INTRODUCTION

The efficient use of information and communication technologies to control the temporal and spatial variability of crop and field parameters is the core of precision agriculture (PA), a modern idea in agricultural management. The non-contact monitoring of agricultural properties is known as remote sensing (RS), and it is based on the radiation reflected by the plants.

By segmenting the orchard canopy, farmers can determine the extent of the canopy and the volume of plants, which helps them make wise crop choices. In a range of scenarios, including varying seasons, tree ages, and weed cover percentages, semantic segmentation seeks to automatically detect and locate the orchard tree canopy. To build the test and train data set for the semantic segmentation database, all of the Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) images are collected. The farming sector gains from semantic segmentation, which automatically extracts tree canopies from aerial photos and provides a tool for the real-time assessment of orchard ecosystems. UAV photos can be used by farmers to measure canopy size, shape, and gaps in the planting pattern, evaluate the quantity of water and pesticides used, ascertain the age of the trees, and predict the orchard's potential yield.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The research done by numerous scientists to evaluate the orchard mapping using different methods is presented in this part.

[1] Laura Elena Cué La Rosa;Dário A. B. Oliveira;Maciel Zortea;Bruno Holtz Gemignani;Raul Queiroz Feitosa. *Learning Geometric Features for Improving the Automatic Detection of Citrus Plantation Rows in UAV Images*. Year: 2022 | Volume: 19 | Journal Article | Publisher: IEEE

The study claims that plantation row detection can be enhanced by using geometric aspects of orchards in UAV photos. The study's primary goal was to train a detection encoder-decoder network (DetED) to recognize RGB photo planting rows. An encoder-decoder correction network (CorrED) is then trained using labeled data to convert binary masks with fictitious row segmentation geometries into adjusted ones. Finally, fix geometric errors in the DetED result using the CorrED network.

[2] Chakraborty Debarun; Deka Bhabesh. *Deep learning-based semantic picture segmentation of the crown of the litchi tree using UAV sensing* Conference Paper, Year: 2023, Publisher: IEEE

This study uses a convolutional neural network to evaluate the potential of UAV sensing and its photogrammetry product-orthomosaic for semantic segmentation of the litchi tree crown. A dataset known

as UAV-Litchi is produced, comprising three thousand 256x256 image patches spread across twelve huge orthomosaics. The U-Net and smooth bending techniques are used to separate the litchi tree's crown. Ultimately, big 3500 x 3500 aerial photos are used for testing in order to provide an comprehensive map of agricultural zone segmentation.

[3] Seema S. Patil; Yuvraj M. Patil; Suhas B. Patil. *Development of Cost-Effective Precision Spraying Techniques Using Sensor Technology Year: 2023 | Conference Paper | Publisher: IEEE*

In the agricultural industry, spraying activities are a very useful instrument for producing crops in a profitable manner. The current spraying methods don't work. In this case, spraying at different speeds is the optimum strategy. The extent of the tree canopy must be precisely estimated in order to apply insecticides at various rates. The different plant sizes and developing structures make it difficult. Throughout their growing seasons, trees display a variety of sizes and shapes. Tree height, width, diameter, and total canopy volume are important variables to consider when assessing this change. This study uses ultrasonic sensors, a controller, and a spraying mechanism that is created proportionately to the volume of the plant to measure the amount of canopy on a tree. The ultrasonic sensor, controller, and spraying mechanism make up the system. The findings revealed no discernible difference between the tree canopy volumes measured by an ultrasonic sensor and by a human. The findings from this study will be useful in selecting and creating the most cost-effective sprayer.

[4] Seema S. Patil; Yuvraj M. Patil; Suhas B. Patil. *Detection and Estimation of Tree Canopy using Deep Learning and Sensor Fusion 2023 International Conference for Advancement in Technology (ICONAT)*

The innovative idea of "precision agriculture" seeks to boost agricultural efficacy and productivity by leveraging cutting-edge information technologies. Growers can now monitor every step of the production process and administer precise treatments chosen by machines with remarkable accuracy thanks to the most recent advancements in automation, artificial intelligence, and networking. Researchers are continuously trying to figure out how to reduce the amount of labor required in agriculture. Precision farming evolves into an intelligent training system that gains knowledge from experience as key information resources advance. Because deep learning networks don't need human intervention, they offer a considerable advantage over earlier algorithms in autonomous feature extraction. LiDAR technology, deep learning, and smart agriculture equipment can all be used to optimize spraying techniques. This study used the ficus, guava, and palm as case studies to design and assesses a canopy detecting and estimation method. The prototype scanned trees for height, distance, classification, and canopy identification using machine vision, sensor fusion, LiDAR, and machine learning. Tree canopy estimation from the smart canopy detection system produced findings with an expected accuracy and average error that were both comparatively low.

[5] Lihong Chang, Hongchao Fan, Ningning Zhu; Zhen Dong. *A Two-Stage Approach for Individual Tree Segmentation From TLS Point Clouds Year: 2022, Volume: 15, Publisher: IEEE*

Applications such as assessing biodiversity in forest sceneries and simulating forest ecosystems require individual tree segmentation. When trees don't grow in layers, the current methods perform effectively. However, if there are large crown overlaps or obstructions to understory plants, they might not survive. This study demonstrates that there are two phases involved in segmenting individual trees. In this, a semantic segmentation module and an instance segmentation module are combined. The point clouds are initially divided into tree and non-tree points by the semantic segmentation network. Object detection and post-processing refinement are added in the second stage using the instance segmentation module.

[6] Ofori, M. El-Gayar, O. *Towards deep learning for weed detection: Deep convolutional neural network architectures for plant seedling classification. August 2020*

The majority of traditional farm weed management methods require manual labor. This approach is expensive, time-consuming, and yields significant losses. However, the traditional method of using

chemicals to control weeds goes against the objective of sustainability. Precision agriculture researchers have employed computer vision to tackle this issue by using remote sensing weed maps; however, this strategy has mostly failed to eradicate weeds in the early seasons because of issues with solar reflection and cloud cover in satellite data. This study used deep convolutional neural networks' autonomous feature extraction capabilities in light of recent developments in artificial intelligence. (DCNNs) for plant seedling classification. According to comparative studies, DCNNs are capable of correctly classifying crops and weeds throughout a variety of phenological growth stages.

[7] Schiefer, F. Kattenborn, T. Frick, A. Frey, J.Schall, P. Koch, B. Schmidlein, S. Mapping forest tree species in high resolution UAV-based RGBimagery by means of convolutional neural networks. *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote. Sens.* 2020

The present study showed that high precision mapping of tree species in diverse temperate forests can be achieved through the combination of RGB imagery from consumer-based UAVs and CNN-based segmentation. The evaluated CNN based tree species mapping encompassed a variety of tile sizes, spatial resolutions and height data (nDSM). When the reference data sample size was adequate, tile size had little impact on model accuracy. The study focused on how CNN-based segmentation techniques interact with high-resolution UAV data. This study showed how UAVs and CNNs can be used in tandem, which presents encouraging opportunities for future uses in forestry or extensive, long-term ecological research.

III.OBJECTIVE

The following objectives have set to achieve the orchard mapping with Deep learning semantic segmentation.

- Development of dataset for semantic segmentation.
- Preprocessing of database images required for semantics segmentation.
- Development of deep learning algorithm for sematic segmentation of target tree.
- Evolution of performance parameter of deep learning based algorithm

IV.PROPOSED WORK

The proposed study will rely on computer vision methods and data-driven algorithms. To generate a vast dataset for supervised learning, the tree canopies in a significant number of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)-collected photos will be masked. An annotated dataset will be the end product of this approach. The model's deep learning algorithm, which will accurately recognize tree canopies and distinguish them from their surrounds, will be trained using this annotated dataset. A mask picture will therefore be created that incorporates the shapes of each target tree canopy. After segmentation, each mask's weighted average will be calculated to establish its centroid. As a rough estimation of the tree trunk, this will be useful.

V. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig 1: System Architecture for Orchard Mapping With Deep Learning Semantic Segmentation

VI. METHODOLOGY

Module 1: Dataset

Train and test sets will be created from the imported data. To implement the strategy, the test set must contain at least one image from each use case.

Module 2: Preprocessing

When employing self-learning algorithms, image pre-processing will be a crucial part of computer vision jobs. The photos must be converted into the proper sizes and shapes in order to carry out the numerical computations. The first step is to reduce the size of each image to 512×512 pixels. Color enhancement will also be applied.

Module 3: U-net algorithm

The model learns to provide appropriate segmentations for every image by feeding the training data into the U-net. To help the trained model learn to produce better segmentation masks, an evaluation measure is applied to a randomly chosen validation set that makes up 10% of the training set. The evaluation metric is employed when the training model creates segmentation masks for the test images.

Module 4: Compare & Predict

False Positive (FP): When trees are incorrectly identified at a location. Not recognizing trees is known as a false negative (FN). The segmentation masks will be compared to the actual masks created during annotation in order to manually check for false positive or false negative segmentations. The accuracy of the trained model on the test data set and the ratio of false positives to false negatives will be used to determine the overall model's performance.

VII. IMPLEMENTATION

1 Dataset

High-resolution aerial photographs of orchards make up the dataset used in this investigation. A drone camera was used to take the pictures. An complete orchard was intended to be covered by each flight in a grid pattern, producing a sequence of overlapping photos. Data was gathered over a period of time to document the orchard's many growth stages.

Fig 2 Orchard Original Image 1

Fig 3 Orchard Original Image 2

Fig 4 Orchard Original Image 3

2 Preprocessing

The steps listed below will be used.

- Open the original photos and the annotations that go with them.
- For every class, translate annotations into binary masks.
- The binary masks should be saved as distinct pictures.

These procedures allowed us to produce precise mask images from the original orchard photos, which are

necessary for deep learning models to be trained for orchard mapping semantic segmentation. By ensuring that the model has access to high-quality, labeled data for learning, this preprocessing improves performance and accuracy in the segmentation tasks that follow.

Fig 5 Orchard Mask Image 1

Fig 6 Orchard Mask Image 2

Fig 7 Orchard Mask Image 3

3 U-net algorithm

The U-Net architecture was selected for this assignment due to its success in segmenting orchard images. To maintain spatial information, the model uses a down-sampling-up sampling structure with skip links. The method includes categorization, bottleneck, up sampling, down sampling, and model building.

4 Results

The following outcomes are obtained after complete processing and the UNET algorithm. A number of metrics are used to assess the following deep learning semantic segmentation model's performance. A dataset of high-resolution aerial photos of several orchards is used to train and evaluate the model. Examples of the original photos, mask images, and anticipated segmentations are displayed in Figures 8 and 9.

Fig 8

Fig 9

VIII. CONCLUSION

In the research project, iation is used. The U-net network algorithm will be used. This makes it easier to automatically recognize and locate the extent of the tree canopy using UAV pictures. Image segmentation will help all farmers by automatically distinguishing tree canopies from aerial pictures for the development of integrated solutions. After these characteristics are measured, the canopy volume of the selected tree can be ascertained.

REFERENCES

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